

pH-metric Studies on the Mixed Ligand Chelates of Oxovanadium (IV) with 2,2'-bipyridyl and Dicarboxylic or Hydroxy acids

A. K. JAIN, V. KUMARI and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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The interaction of vanadyl ion with 2,2'-bipyridyl and some dicarboxylic or hydroxy acids (where dicarboxylic acid=oxalic (OX), malonic (MALN), phthalic (PHA), maleic (MAL) acids; hydroxy acids= salicylic (SA), 5-sulfosalicylic (5-SSA), mandelic (MAND) and glycollic (HG) acids) was studied potentiometrically. pH-titrations of the reaction mixtures containing vanadyl sulphate, 2,2'-bipyridyl and one of the dicarboxylic or hydroxy acids (OX, MALN, PHA, MAL, SA, 5-SSA, MAND and HG acids) in equimolar ratio exhibited the formation of 1:1:1 mixed ligand chelates. The formation constants of the resulting biligand chelates were calculated, at $35 \pm 1^\circ$ and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ and also the thermodynamic functions viz., ΔF , ΔH and ΔS ($\mu = 0.1M$ KNO₃).

In the earlier communication¹ the results of the potentiometric studies on the ternary system, VO²⁺ - IMDA-Dicarboxylic or Hydroxy acids were reported. Similar studies have been extended on the ternary systems VO²⁺ - bipy-Dicarboxylic or hydroxy acids (dicarboxylic acids=OX, MALN, PHA, MAL acids; hydroxy acids=SA, SSA, MAND and HG acids) and the interesting results have been discussed in the present communication.

Experimental

Materials :

All the chemicals used were either of AR (BDH) or GR (S. Merck) grade. A stock solution of vanadyl sulphate was prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized by titration against KMnO₄ solution. Solutions of 2,2'-bipyridyl, OX, MALN, PHA, MAL, SA, 5-SSA, MAND and HG acids were prepared by direct weighing. 2,2'-bipyridyl was used as its monohydrochloride obtained by adding calculated volume of standard HCl to the calculated weighed amount of 2,2'-bipyridyl. 5-SSA was used as its monosodium salt. The concentrations of all the ligands were checked by pH-titration against 0.1 M KOH solution.

Method :

The pH-titrations were carried out at $35 \pm 1^\circ$ and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ (thermostatically maintained), with a precision Philips pH-meter (model PR 9405 M) with working accuracy ± 0.02 , using standard calomel electrode (PV 9021) and glass electrode (PV 9011) consisting of a thin walled bulb of soft glass containing hydrochloric acid into which a small silver electrode dips. The pH of the unknown solution

$$-\log_{10} H^+ = pH = \frac{E_o - E_c}{0.0591}$$

where E_o is the observed potential and E_c is the potential of the calomel electrode under the experimental conditions.

Ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M$ KNO₃), the total volume (50 ml) and the concentration (0.025 M in ligand and metal ion) were always kept constant at the beginning of the electrometric titration. Each titration was performed in duplicate in order to establish the reproducibility of the measurements.

Calculations :

The acid dissociation constants of the dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell² and the stability constants ($\log K_{MLL'}$) of the ternary systems by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa³. Thermodynamic functions viz., free energy of formation (ΔF), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) were calculated by the following expressions

$$\Delta F = -RT \ln K_{MLL'} \quad (\text{where } R \text{ and } T \text{ are the gas constant and temperature in absolute degrees respectively})$$

(T_1 and T_2 are temperature in absolute degree and β_1 and β_2 are the constants at T_1 & T_2 respectively)

$$\Delta H = \frac{2.303 R T_1 T_2 (\log \beta_2 - \log \beta_1)}{T_2 - T_1}$$

$$\text{and } \Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta F}{T}$$

The pK values of the ligands, the formation constants and the values of thermodynamic functions (ΔF , ΔH and ΔS) are recorded in table 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS

Ligand	pK ₁	pK ₂
2,2'-bipy hydrochloride	4.54 ± 0.07 (t=35°) 4.69 ± 0.09 (t=45°) (4.437)	—
Oxalic acid	1.54 ± 0.19 (1.24 ⁸)	4.10 ± 0.06 (4.10 ⁸)
Malonic acid	2.73 ± 0.10 (2.75 ⁹)	5.34 ± 0.09 (5.36 ⁹)
Phthalic acid	3.16 ± 0.08 (3.10 ¹⁰)	5.40 ± 0.12 (5.29 ¹⁰)
Maleic acid	1.98 ± 0.16 (1.92 ¹¹)	6.36 ± 0.04 (6.22 ¹¹)
Salicylic acid	3.01 ± 0.08 (2.97 ¹²)	13.60 ¹²
5-Sulfosalicylic acid	2.70 ± 0.06 (2.68 ⁶)	11.40 ± 0.04 (11.42 ⁶)
Glycollic acid	3.75 ± 0.12 (3.71 ¹⁴)	11.11 ± 0.05

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS (log K_{MLL'})

System	log K _{MLL'} 35°	log K _{MLL'} 45°
VO ²⁺ - bipy - OX	8.88 ± 0.15	8.48 ± 0.12
VO ²⁺ - bipy - MALN	11.34 ± 0.19	11.02 ± 0.17
VO ²⁺ - bipy - PHA	10.97 ± 0.27	10.70 ± 0.24
VO ²⁺ - bipy - MAL	11.44 ± 0.17	11.00 ± 0.24
VO ²⁺ - bipy - SA	27.78 ± 0.22	27.42 ± 0.20
VO ²⁺ - bipy - SSA	22.93 ± 0.22	22.62 ± 0.20
VO ²⁺ - bipy - HG	23.26 ± 0.20	22.99 ± 0.25

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTION VIZ., ΔF, ΔH, AND ΔS

System	ΔF(Kcal/mole)		ΔH(Kcal/mole)		ΔS(cal/mole/degree)	
	35°	45°	35°	45°	35°	45°
VO ²⁺ - bipy - OX	-12.51	-12.33	-17.92	-17.56	-17.57	
VO ²⁺ - bipy - MALN	-15.97	-15.60	-14.23	+ 5.65	+ 4.30	
VO ²⁺ - bipy - PHA	-15.45	-15.56	-12.09	+10.90	+10.91	
VO ²⁺ - bipy - MAL	-16.11	-16.00	-19.71	-11.68	-11.67	
VO ²⁺ - bipy - SA	-39.14	-38.89	-16.13	+74.70	+71.25	
VO ²⁺ - bipy - SSA	-32.30	-32.91	-13.88	+59.80	+59.84	
VO ²⁺ - bipy - HG	-32.77	-33.45	-12.09	+67.11	+67.16	

Results and Discussion

The curves for the systems VO²⁺ - bipy-OX, and VO²⁺ - bipy-SA are exhibited in the figs. 1 and 2, as representative, whereas the curves for other systems have been omitted for the sake of brevity.

Fig. 1: Curve a-bipy hydrochloride; b-1:1, VO(IV)-bipy c-1:1, VO(IV)-OX; d-1:1:1, VO(IV)-bipy-OX

Fig. 2: Curve c'-1:1, VO(IV)-SA; d'-1:1:1, VO(IV)-bipy-SA → indicates appearance of turbidity.

→ indicates disappearance of the precipitate

Curve a, fig. 1, showing the potentiometric titration of bipyridyl hydrochloride with KOH, exhibits a sharp inflexion at m=1 (m being the moles of base added per mole of the metal ion or ligand), indicating that the ligand acts as a monobasic acid.

Curve b, fig. 1, representing the potentiometric titration of vanadyl sulphate with KOH in the presence of an equimolar amount of 2,2'-bipyridyl exhibits an ill-defined inflexion at about m=2, which probably indicates that the reaction involving the formation of 1:1 complex and its hydrolysis overlap⁴.

The curve c/c' (figs. 1 & 2) representing the titrations of vanadyl sulphate with KOH in the presence of an equimolar amount of dicarboxylic acids (OX, MALN, PHA and MAL acids) and hydroxy acids (SA, 5-SSA, MAND and HG acids), may be interpreted in terms of the formation of 1:1 binary complexes and their hydrolysis as reported earlier⁵⁻⁶.

Mixed ligand chelates :

The curve d/d', (figs. 1 & 2) represent the 1:1 VO²⁺ - bipy-OX/SA systems respectively.

Following possibilities were considered while interpreting the curves d/d', for the ternary systems.

- (i) The formation of the binary complexes of the metal ion with both the ligands i.e., 2,2'-bipyridyl/ Dicarboxylic or hydroxy acid, separately ;
- (ii) the formation of a complex with a stronger ligand, the other ligand remaining free ;

- (iii) the addition of the two ligands to the metal ion in distinct steps, the binary complex of the metal ion with the stronger ligand being formed as an intermediate species ; and
- (iv) the simultaneous addition of both the ligands to the metal ion forming a biligand complex.

Assuming the formation of the two binary complexes, the resulting curve d/d' representing the ternary systems would be lying between the curve b for VO^{2+} -bipy and curve c/c' for VO^{2+} -dicarboxylic/hydroxy acid. This is not the case.

The second possibility may be excluded by comparison of the curve d/d' representing the ternary systems with a composite curve (drawn by adding horizontal distances of the curve c/c' representing the binary complex with the stronger ligand and the curve a for the other ligand i.e., bipy. Moreover, the curve for the mixed system would overlap with the curve representing the binary complex with either of the ligands. This is also not observed.

The stepwise complex formation, if any, would indicate clear steps in the ternary complex curve, identifying the addition of the two ligands. This is also not indicated in the systems studied.

Thus the formation of the mixed ligand chelate by simultaneous addition of the ligands appears to be the only possibility in the systems studied. The formation of the mixed ligand complex is further supported by the lowering of *pH* in comparison to the binary systems in the region of mixed ligand complex formation and also by the significant color changes observed during the titration.

In these systems, due to the appearance of a solid phase at about $m=2.5$, calculations could not be made at $m>2$. In the case of VO^{2+} -bipy-MAND acid system, the turbidity, however, appears at $m \approx 0.4$ and therefore no calculations could be performed.

A sharp inflexion at $m \approx 3$ in the titration curve d/d' for the mixed ligand systems discussed above, may be attributed to the complete neutralization of protons of 2,2'-bipyridyl and dicarboxylic or hydroxy

Fig. 3

acid, made labile as a result of chelation. Considering VO^{2+} -bipy-OX/SA systems as representative, the overall reaction may be represented as shown in Fig. 3.

A comparison of the data given in table 2 indicates the order of stability of the ternary complexes in terms of dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids—

- (1) Malonic acid > Oxalic acid
- (2) Maleic acid > Phthalic acid
- (3) Salicylic acid > 5-sulfosalicylic acid

The relative stabilities of the mixed ligand chelates involving malonic and oxalic, maleic and phthalic acids follow the order of the basicities of these ligands. In the case of complexes of SA and 5-SSA, the relative order may be explained on the basis of the presence of sulphonic group in 5-SSA and the steric factors. The sulphonic group increases the acidity of the phenolic group and probably results in the formation of less stable complexes. The steric factor increases with the increasing size of the ligand and therefore decreases the stability of the resulting chelate.

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References

1. A. K. JAIN, R. C. SHARMA and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *Polish Journal of Chemistry*, 1978, 52, 259.
2. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74 5052.
3. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 1971, 9(4), 381.
4. R. L. DUTTA and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44(4), 2666.
5. S. P. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Acta Chimica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae, Tomus*, 1974, 80(4), 425.
6. S. P. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Bulletin De L' Academie, Polonaise Des Sciences*, 1974, XXII, No. 8, 725.
7. KRUMHOLZ, *Nature*, 1949, 163, 724.
8. DAWSON, HOSKINS and SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1884, 2530.
9. GANE and INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 127, 1691.
10. MAXWELL and PARTINGTON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 922.
11. BRANCH and CALVIN, "The Theory of Organic Chemistry", Prentice Hall, Inc., New York 1941.
12. BABKO, *J. Gen. Chem. (USSR)*, 1947, 17, 443.
13. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, *Stability Constant*, 2nd Edn. London, The Chemical Society 1964.
14. CANNAN and KIBRICK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2314.